

Synthesis of 3-Substituted Coumarins. Part I.

D. Chakravarti and R. Das

A number of 3-amino and 3-hydroxy coumarins with various substituents in the benzene ring have been synthesised with a view to studying their bacteriostatic and fungistatic properties.

The pharmacological and physiological activities of 3-amino coumarins have attracted wide spread attention in recent years with the isolation and study of the structure of the antibiotic novobiocin¹⁻⁴, a complex 3-amino-4-hydroxy coumarin derivative. Following the discovery of the excellent bacteriostatic properties⁵ of the antibiotic, there was increasing interest in the synthesis and investigations on the biochemical properties of simpler 3-amino-4-hydroxy coumarins. Recently, Rao and Rao^{6,7} studied the antifungal and antibacterial actions of a number of synthetic 3-amino-4-hydroxy coumarins substituted in the phenyl ring, N-substituted 3-amino-4-hydroxy coumarins and coumarino-(3,4)-oxazoles as analogues of novobiocin and reported some interesting results.

Rodighiero and Antonello⁸ showed the bacterial inhibition of 3-amino coumarins without any hydroxy group in 4-position (but having hydroxyl group or groups in the phenyl nucleus). The observation made by them that 3-amino-7,8-dihydroxy coumarin possesses good antibacterial activity has prompted the present authors to undertake the synthesis and study of physiological activities of 3-amino coumarins having no hydroxyl group either in the α -pyrone or in the phenyl ring.

The method used for the synthesis of 3-acetamido coumarins (I), which are intermediates for 3-amino and 3-hydroxy derivatives is the condensation of ortho hydroxy aldehydes containing various types of substituents with glycine in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate and acetic anhydride. The conditions applied were similar to those of Rodighiero *et al.*⁸ with slight variation in the temperature and time of heating. The same condensation has been extended successfully in the case of ortho-hydroxy aldehyde of naphthalene system.

1. Kaczka *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 4125.
2. Hinman, Caron and Hoeksema, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 3789.
3. Vaartaza *Phytopathology*, 1960, **50**, 870.
4. Seneca, *Antibiotics Ann.*, 1955, 697.
5. Frost *et al.*, *Antibiotics Annual 1955-56*, p. 919.
6. K. S. R. Krishna Mohan Rao and N. V. Subba Rao, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, **3**, 522.
7. K. S. R. Krishna Mohan Rao and N. V. Subba Rao, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.* Vol. LXVII (1968), 42.
8. G. Rodighiero and C. Antonello, *Bull. Chim. Farm.*, 1958, **97**, 592.

The condition of hydrolysis of 3-acetamido coumarins is a very important factor in synthesising the 3-amino compounds (II). The authors failed to isolate the 3-amino derivatives by refluxing with 3*N* HCl as described by Rodighiero *et al.*⁸ but instead obtained the compounds identified to be the corresponding 3-hydroxy coumarins (III). Only in a few cases, controlled hydrolysis with 3*N* HCl produced the 3-amino coumarins. Thus only 3-amino-7-methoxy and 3-amino-8-methoxy coumarins were obtained from their respective 3-acetamido compounds by refluxing slowly with 3*N* HCl for 10 mins. Hydrolysis of 3-acetamido coumarins to 3-hydroxy products by 3*N* HCl was also observed by Trivedi and Sethna⁹.

However, it was possible to get the desired 3-amino coumarin derivatives by hydrolysing the 3-acetamido compounds with (1 : 1) 50% H₂SO₄ (by volume) and acetic acid at 50–60° for thirty to fortyfive minutes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of 3-acetamido coumarins : An intimate mixture of the salicylaldehyde derivative (1 part), glycine (0.5 part), fused sodium acetate (1.25 parts) and freshly distilled acetic anhydride (5 parts) was heated in an oil bath at 140° for 1 hr. The temperature was gradually raised and heating was continued for 1 hr more at 160°. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to 100° and poured into water containing cracked ice. The whole was kept overnight and the solid separated was washed with very dil. NaOH solution, with cold water, a few ml. of hot methanol and crystallised from acetic acid (Table I). Yield 20–45%.

3-Amino coumarins : 3-Acetamido coumarin derivative (1 g.) was suspended in acetic acid (25 ml) and 50% sulphuric acid (25 ml) and heated at 50–60° for 30–45 mins. The clear solution was poured in equal volume of cold water and neutralised with sodium bicarbonate. The amorphous free amino product was washed and crystallised from dil. alcohol (Table II). Yield 50–90%.

9. K. N. Trivedi, and S. Sethna *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25** 1817.
10. F. W. Lynch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, **101**, 1758.
11. Roy and Mahajani, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **33**, 455.

TABLE I

3-Acetamido coumarin derivatives

Aldehydes	3-Acetamido coumarins	m.p. °C	Formula	Analysis Nitrogen %	
				Found	Calcd.
2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde	5,6-benzo	247	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₃ N	5.48	5.53
5-Methyl salicylaldehyde	6-methyl	214	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₃ N	6.42	6.45
4-Methyl salicylaldehyde	7-methyl	182	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₃ N	6.44	6.45
3-Methyl salicylaldehyde	8-methyl	210	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₃ N	6.40	6.45
5-Chloro-salicylaldehyde	6-chloro	265	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₃ N Cl	5.91	5.89
3-Chloro-salicylaldehyde	8-chloro	235	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₃ N Cl	5.77	5.89
5-Chloro-4,6-dimethyl-salicylaldehyde	5,7-dimethyl-6-chloro	> 300	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ O ₃ N Cl	5.39	5.27
5-Bromo-salicylaldehyde	6-bromo ^a	263	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₃ N Br	5.00	4.96
3,5-Dibromosalicylaldehyde	6,8-dibromo ^b	277-78	C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₃ N Br ₂	4.00	3.89
<i>o</i> -vanillin	8-methoxy	234	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	6.17	6.00
5-Bromo- <i>o</i> -vanillin	6-bromo-8-methoxy	230	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₄ N Br	4.69	4.48
5-Nitro- <i>o</i> -vanillin	6-nitro-8-methoxy	284-86	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₆ N ₂	10.27	10.07
4-Methoxy salicylaldehyde	7-methoxy	230	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	6.20	6.00
6-Hydroxy-piperonal	6,7-methylene dioxy.	> 265	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₅ N	5.61	5.66

^a Trivedi and Sethna⁹ reported the m.p. as 261-62° prepared by condensation with acetyl glycine.

^b The above authors⁹ reported the m.p. as 279°.

TABLE II

3-Amino coumarins and their benzoyl derivatives

3-Amino coumarins	m.p. °C	Formula	Analysis Nitrogen %		3-Benzamido coumarins with formulae	m.p. °C	Analysis Nitrogen %	
			Found	Calcd.			Found	Calcd.
5,6-Benzo	159	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N	6.70	6.63	5,6-benzo C ₂₀ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	230	4.39	4.44
6-Methyl	160	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ N	8.21	8.00	6-methyl C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	171	4.93	5.01
7-Methyl	136-37	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ N	8.01	8.00	7-methyl C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	163	5.32	5.01
8-Methyl	80	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ N	7.77	8.00				
6-Chloro	204	C ₉ H ₈ O ₂ N Cl	6.83	7.16				
8-Chloro	134	C ₉ H ₈ O ₂ N Cl	7.31	7.16	8-Chloro C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₃ Cl N	210	4.44	4.67
6-Chloro-5,7-dimethyl	176	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N Cl	6.13	6.26	6-chloro-5,7-dimethyl C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₃ N Cl	246	4.36	4.27
6-Bromo ^c	206	C ₉ H ₈ O ₂ N Br	5.88	5.83				
6,8-Dibromo	164	C ₈ H ₅ O ₂ N Br ₂	4.13	4.38	6,8-dibromo C ₁₇ H ₉ O ₃ N Br ₂	235	3.40	3.21
8-Methoxy ^d	195	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₃ N	7.19	7.32				
8-Methoxy-6-bromo	162	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₃ N Br	5.18	5.18	8-methoxy-6-bromo C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₄ N Br	242	4.00	3.74
6-Nitro-8-methoxy	161	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₅ N ₂	11.84	11.86	6-nitro-8-methoxy C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₆ N ₂	243	8.00	8.23
7-Methoxy	154	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₃ N	7.22	7.32	7-methoxy C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	166	4.62	4.74
6,7-Methylene-dioxy.	229	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₄ N	6.99	6.82				

^c The m.p. of the compound prepared by Lynch¹⁰ by a different method was reported as 205°.

^d Roy and Mahajani¹¹ prepared the compound by a different method and reported the m.p. 201°.

3-Hydroxy coumarins: 3-Acetamido coumarin derivative (2 g.) in alcohol (50 ml) and 3*N* HCl (100 ml) was refluxed for 5 hrs and filtered hot. The crystals separated on cooling were washed and crystallised from alcohol (Table III).

TABLE III

3-Hydroxy coumarins

3-Hydroxy coumarins	m.p. °C	Formula	Analysis		IR spectra (Nujol) ν_{max} cm ⁻¹	Acetyl derivatives
			Found	Calcd.		
5,6-Benzo	233	C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₃	C, 73.29 H, 3.59	C, 73.58 H, 3.77	3350, 1700, 1640, 1590, 1525, 1460.	m.p. 160° (alcohol) Found: C, 71.21; H, 4.2. C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₄ requires C, 70.86; H 3.93.
6-Methyl	190	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₃	C, 68.31 H, 4.50	C, 68.18 H, 4.54	3350, 1690, 1630, 1580, 1490.	
7-Methyl	151-52	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₃	C, 68.01 H, 4.51	C, 68.18 H, 4.54		
8-Methyl	174	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₃	C, 68.31 H, 4.64	C, 68.18 H, 4.54		
6-Chloro	252	C ₉ H ₅ O ₃ Cl	C, 54.62 H, 2.70	C, 54.96 H, 2.54	3350, 1710, 1630, 1610, 1560, 1480, 912, 880, 815, 770, 755.	m.p. 135° (alcohol) Found: Cl, 14.63. C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₄ Cl, requires Cl, 14.88.
8-Chloro	201	C ₉ H ₅ O ₃ Cl	C, 54.66 H, 2.66	C, 54.96 H, 2.54	3300, 1700, 1640, 1600, 1565, 960, 920, 885, 765, 725.	m.p. 153° (alc.) Found: Cl, 14.55. C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₄ Cl, requires Cl, 14.88.
6-Chloro-5, 7-dimethyl.	222-23	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₃ Cl	C, 58.38 H, 4.13	C, 58.79 H, 4.00		
8-Methoxy	178	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₄	C, 62.21 H, 4.00	C, 62.51 H, 4.16		m.p. 118° (alc.) Found: C, 61.40; H, 4.51 C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₆ requires C, 61.53; H, 4.26.
8-Methoxy-6 bromo	230	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₄ Br	Br, 29.31	Br, 29.52		m.p. 170° (alc.) Found: Br, 25.89. C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₅ Br requires Br, 25.55.
6-Nitro-8- methoxy	224-26	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₆ N	N, 6.01	N, 5.90		
7-Methoxy	(d) 175	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₄	C, 62.33 H, 4.01	C, 62.50 H, 4.16		

As characteristic derivatives, benzylation of 3-amino coumarins was done by usual Schotten-Baumann's method and the acetyl derivatives of 3-hydroxy products were prepared by heating with acetic anhydride in pyridine.

It has been observed that the yield and nature of the condensation products are improved when nitro and halogen substituents are present in the aldehydes.

All the 3-hydroxy coumarins in alcohol give green coloration with ferric chloride and have been found to couple with diazotised aromatic amines giving brilliant red dyes.

The antibacterial and antifungal actions of the 3-amino and 3-hydroxy coumarin derivatives will be reported in a separate communication.

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